

Silver nanoparticle doped dendrimer/DNA nanogel – A novel approach of getting assembled metal nanoparticle in solution

Atanu Mitra

Department of Materials Science, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail : drmitra04@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : The synthesis and characterization of poly (amido amine) dendrimer/DNA nanogel containing silver nanoparticle have been reported. Initially dendrimer protected-nanoscale silver particles have been synthesized in aqueous medium. UV-Vis spectra and transmission electron micrograph indicate almost spherical silver particles with an average diameter 6 ± 2 nm were formed. The preformed dendrimer protected silver nanoparticle solution was mixed with DNA solution to fabricate the dendrimer/DNA complex. At the dendrimer/DNA-mixing ratio (number ratio of NH_2 groups in dendrimer vs phosphate groups in DNA) 0.3, aggregates (nanogel) were formed. Transmission micrograph revealed the presence of silver nanoparticles inside that gel matrix. Binding of dendrimer molecule with DNA chain occurs through electrostatic interaction. This kind of approach promises the development of polyelectrolyte-based soluble conductive nanowires and three dimensionally self-assembled complex nanostructure.

Keywords : Nanoparticle, dendrimer, silver.

Synthesis and characterization of metal nanoparticles are subjects of growing interest from fundamental and applied viewpoints. The applications of these nanoparticles have introduced a remarkable development in the field of medicine, catalysis, optoelectronics and many other areas of science and technology¹. Silver nanoparticles are very attracting, since they show the distinctive properties, such as high catalytic activity, excellent conductivity, good antibacterial and optical properties. Owing to these unique properties silver nanoparticles may have potential application in chemical, electronic and optical sensors, information storage materials, antibacterial coatings of medical implant etc.². It has been suggested that the ability to control the assembly of nanoparticles in solution and at patterned substrates will allow aspects of the technological potential of these materials to be fully exploited. A number of key developments, which represent progress toward these goals, have appeared in literature³. One such development involves using high-information-content biomolecules, including DNA and proteins, to program the assembly of nanoparticles in solution. The functionalised nanoparticles may be attached to the polyelectrolyte chain either by electrostatic interaction or by covalent bonding. DNA-templated nanowires of silver⁴, platinum⁵, palladium⁶ have been reported in

very recent literature.

Among various methods of metal nanoparticle preparation, the chemical reduction of metal salts in their liquid phase is the most convenient method whereby metal ions are reduced by a reducing agent such as sodium borohydride, sodium citrate, hydrogen etc. Unfortunately, colloids tend to aggregate in solution because of their small size. One of the effective strategies to avoid this is to protect colloids with protective agents such as thiols, surfactants, polymers, and polyelectrolytes, which can control particle size, prevent agglomeration, and introduce functionality to the particle surface. Dendrimers are a new class of monodisperse macromolecules with regular and highly branched three-dimensional architecture and surface functionality⁷ and have found increasing applications in nanoscience as a new type of potential template for the formation of inorganic nanoclusters^{8,9}.

In the present work, a unique approach of controlled assembly of silver nanoparticles in solution using DNA has been described. Initially fourth generation (G4) poly (amido amine) (PAMAM) dendrimer protected nanoscale silver particles have been synthesized in aqueous medium at pH 6.5. Attempt is made to prepare assembly of these silver nanoparticles through the formation of dendrimer/

DNA complex. The nanoparticle and their assembly in the dendrimer/DNA gel have been examined by transmission electron microscope (TEM).

Experimental

Silver nitrate (AgNO_3 , 99.99%), sodium borohydride (NaBH_4 , 99%) were purchased from Loba Chemicals. Methanol solution of amine-terminated fourth generation (G4) PAMAM dendrimer was purchased from Aldrich Chemical Co. Sodium salt of salmon testes DNA (base pair weight 660) was obtained from Sigma Chemical Company. All of these chemicals were used without modification. Double distilled water was used throughout all experiments. Dendrimer-protected silver nanoparticle was synthesized according to the procedure described in the literature⁹. For a typical experiment, 2 cm³ of freshly prepared 2.5 mM AgNO_3 was added to 5 cm³ of aqueous solution of dendrimer of various concentration and solutions were stirred for 15 min. Then 0.6 cm³ of 0.02 mol dm⁻³ freshly prepared sodium borohydride was added to the solutions under stirring for 30 min to obtain the Ag-nanoparticles in solution. The mixed solutions were prepared by adding an aqueous solution of dendrimer-protected Ag nanoparticle solution at pH 6.5 into an aqueous solution of DNA, where the DNA concentration was kept constant at 6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$. The whole experiment was performed at room temperature. Mixing ratios of the dendrimer to DNA were determined on the basis of the number of terminal NH_2 groups in the dendrimer vs the number of phosphate groups in the DNA, $[\text{NH}_2]/[\text{PO}_4^-]$.

UV-visible absorption spectra were performed by spectrometrically (Shimazu 2401PC). The TEM images were obtained with a JEOL, JEM 2010 transmission electron microscope operating at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Samples for TEM analyses were prepared by placing a small drop of colloidal solutions on carbon coated copper TEM grids. After 10 mins of the deposition of the film on TEM grid, the excess solution was removed using a blotting paper and grid was allowed to dry prior to measurement.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1a shows the UV-Vis absorption spectra of the dendrimer protected silver colloidal solution. A dilute colloidal silver solution of low metal to dendrimer ratio displays a strong absorption in the 415 nm regions. This peak must arise from the surface plasmon absorption of the silver clusters. Silver metals are known to have intense plasmon absorption bands in the visible region. A TEM image of the dendrimer-passivated silver

nanoparticles is shown in Fig 1b. Random distribution of almost spherical particles with an average diameter of 6 ± 2 nm was seen. This indicates that dendrimers in the solution are not ordered in the experimental conditions.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. (a) UV-Vis spectra of dendrimer protected silver nanoparticle (b) TEM micrograph of the dendrimer protected silver nanoparticle

TEM images of dendrimer/DNA complex containing silver particle with nanoscale size presented in Figs. 2 and 3. The dendritic growth of dendrimer/DNA complex on the TEM grid is obvious from Fig. 2. Fig. 3 shows the detailed view of the inside of the complex. The images clearly inferred that silver nanoparticles with almost similar morphologies with particles in Fig. 1b are dispersed inside the complex. Previously Mitra *et al.*¹⁰ exhibited that the dendrimer/DNA complexes formed aggregates (nanogels) when the mixing ratio was increased above 0.2. They studied the morphology of the complexes adsorbed on mica surface by atomic force microscopy. From AFM images it was seen that large aggregates were the cross-linked fiber networks of dendrimer/DNA complexes, which are, nanogels. Almost spherical morphology of the nanogel was reported. In contrast in the present study the TEM images (Fig. 2) show the den-

Fig. 2. TEM image of silver nanoparticle containing dendrimer/DNA complex (general view in large scale).

Fig. 3. TEM image of silver nanoparticle containing dendrimer/DNA aggregate (proposed nanogel).

dritic morphology of the nanogels. The poor wetting property of aqueous solvent to hydrophobic carbon surface of TEM grid may cause the change of sphere to dendritic morphology of the nanogel. Here successfully the silver nanoclusters have been incorporated inside these nanogels. It is clear from TEM image (vide Fig. 3) that the interparticle distance is irregular. So from the basis of our experimental results it is concluded that a disordered-assembly of nanoparticles in solution has been obtained. In this direction further experiments will be needed

to get an ordered-assembly of metal nanoparticle where the interparticle distance should be same. The most interesting achievement is that the assembly of metal nanoclusters according to the dendrimer/DNA complex structure has been obtained in solution phase. This idea can be extended for the preparation of the assembly of other metal nanoclusters using various polyelectrolyte complexes.

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